

MICROBIAL ASSESSMENT OF GROUND MELON PRESERVED WITH SALTS

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ABSTRACT

Microbial assessment of ground melon preserved with some salts (sodium chloride, sodium citrate and a mixture of sodium chloride and sodium citrate) was evaluated. The results revealed that after 5 days, there were no changes in the microbial quality of the ground melon. However, both the preserved and the control (unpreserved) melon samples changed from milk to brown colour after 31 days. The melon preserved with 10% sodium citrate had the highest mean plate count of 8.0×10^7 cfu/g while the one preserved with 10% sodium chloride had the mean plate count of 5.0×10^7 cfu/g. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Aspergillus niger* were isolated from the preserved and the control (unpreserved) samples.

Key note: Microbial Assessment, Ground Melon preserved, salt.

INTRODUCTION

Melon (*Colocynthis citrullus vulgaris*) belongs to the *Cucubitaceae*. The family is composed of many species of vine crops with spreading growth habits and all are warm season annual crops (Abaclu, 1979 and (Orji *et al.*, 2006;). It is widely cultivated in Nigeria mainly for its seeds from where a number of products could be obtained. The seeds are edible and it is eaten in virtually all parts of Nigeria and in many other parts of the world (Oyolu, 1977 and Orji, *et al.*, 2006).

In the southern parts of Nigeria, the seeds are processed into Ogiri (food condiment); and melon cake (Agbarati) (Odunfa, 1982; Uzoigwe & kwealor, 2002).

The major problem that besets melon seeds is that it deteriorates quickly in storage due to microbial infection. The effect of fungal attack on melon seeds include changes in colour and decrease in the nutritional value (Abaclu, 1979). In 1980, Alamenda observed that 1% decrease in moisture content doubles the shelf life of the melon seeds; which means that moisture content plays an important role in maintaining the quality of melon stored. When the excess water in the melon is dried up, the level of activities of the microorganisms present will be reduced.

However, the ground melon just like every other indigenous food products is prone to microbial contamination and spoilage. Therefore, some food preservatives could be used to slow down microbial growth, give the desired texture and appearance, preserve the nutritional quality and increase the shelf life of the melon ((Abbas and Card, 1980, Herbert, 1986; and Angelidis and Smith, 2003).

The aim of this work was to investigate the microbial quality of ground melon preserved with different salts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples: Dried dehulled melon seeds were obtained from Ekpoma main market. The melon seeds were collected with sterile double layers of polyethene bags and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

PROCESSING OF THE MELON SEEDS

The dehulled melon seeds were rinsed in tap water to remove dust and other particles; then dried in the hot air oven at 160°C for 30 minutes. The dried

seeds were then ground with a blender (which has been disinfected with methylated spirit) into powder form and kept in a double layer air-tight polyethene bags.

The ground melon seeds were divided into four (4) parts. One part was without additives (0%) i.e., control sample and the other three parts, each was divided into three subparts and treated with the additives.

1. To the first part was added Sodium Chloride.
2. To the second part was added Sodium Citrate.
3. To the third part was added a combination of Sodium Chloride and Sodium Citrate (50g of each of the salts were combined to give 100g of the samples which was well mixed before it was applied).

The melon was observed for any deterioration at 24 hours interval, until loss of organoleptic qualities were noticed. The rate of spoilage and shelf life were recorded for the treated samples.

The control sample was also preserved to examine the physical changes. After the salt was added to the melon, they were put into the universal sterile bottles and left on a bench while being analysed on every 24 hours for 5 days for physical changes and microbial contamination that can cause spoilage.

Microbiological Analysis

The sterility of the ground melon was determined by streak inoculation of the ground melon onto Nutrient agar, Mac Conkey agar and Sabouraud dextrose agar at 30°C for 24 hours and 28°C overnight for SDA. Plates were examined for growth of any contamination in order to avoid false positive results.

One gram of each of the samples was weighed and placed in a universal bottle containing 9ml of distilled water to get a stock solution. These were serially diluted in ten-fold dilution.

A loopful of stock solution was used to inoculate plates of nutrient agar (oxoid), Mac Conkey agar (oxoid) using standard spread plate culture technique (Collee and Miles, 1989; Ogbulie *et al*, 1998). The plates were incubated at 32°C for 24 hours for plates of nutrient agar and Mac Conkey agar and 3 - 4 days for plates of Sabouraud dextrose agar respectively. 1ml from the various dilutions were used to inoculate plates of nutrient agar and Sabouraud dextrose agar using Standard Pour Plate Culture method (Collee and Miles, 1989, Ogbulie *et al*, 1998) for total viable count. The plates were examined for growth after incubation. Pure cultures of the bacteria isolated were identified based on cultural, morphological and biochemical characteristics (Kerr, 1981; Collee and Miles, 1989; Holt *et al*, 1994).

The fungal isolate was identified with reference to their appearance on cultural morphology under the light microscope after been stained with lactophenol cotton blue (Barnett and Hunter, 1972).

RESULTS

The mean total plate or viable count of the ground melon for the period of preservation of the samples treated with different concentrations of the additives used and the control samples are shown in Table 2. The samples preserved with sodium chloride at a concentration of 2.5%, 5.0% and 10.0% were 1.0×10^5 , 2.5×10^4 and 4.5×10^3 cfu/g respectively; the samples treated with sodium citrate at various concentration were 3.5×10^5 , 5.0×10^6 and 8.0×10^7 cfu/g respectively; The samples treated with the combination of sodium chloride and sodium citrate at various concentrations of 2.5%,

5.0% and 10.0% were 3.1×10^5 , 2.5×10^5 and 1.8×10^6 cfu/g respectively (Table 2) while the control sample had 1.2×10^8 cfu/g (Table 2).

The physical changes of the ground melon preserved with both salts and the control samples are shown in (Table 1). The colour of the samples treated with various concentrations of the salts were normal within 5 days of the preservation period and changed from milk to brown colour after 31 days (Table 1). In addition, the samples treated with 10.0% concentration of the combined sodium chloride and sodium citrate was noticed to have offensive odour including the control samples (Table 1).

Two bacterial genera - *Staphylococcus* and *Klebsiella* and a fungus *Aspergillus niger* were isolated from both the control and the treated samples

Table 1: The physical changes of the ground melon after 31days of preservation.

SAMPLE TYPE	CONCENTRATION Percentage (%)	OBSERVATION				
		Ohr	24hrs	48hrs	5days	31days
Melon only(control sample)	0	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC,OO
Melon + sodium chloride	2.5%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	5.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	10.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
Melon + Sodium citrate	2.5%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	5.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	10.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
Melon + Sodium Chloride + Sodium Citrate	2.5%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	5.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC
	10.0%	NC	NC	NC	NC	BC,OO

KEY

NC - No change

BC - Brown colour

OO- Offensive odour

Table 2: The mean Total Viable Count per gram of Ground melon (cfu/g)

SAMPLE TYPE	CONCENTRATION	MEAN COLONY FORMING UNIT/GRAM (cfu/g)
Control Sample	0%	1.2×10^8
Melon + Sodium Chloride	2.5	1.0×10^5
	5.0	2.5×10^4
	10.0	4.5×10^3
Melon + sodium Citrate	2.5	3.5×10^5
	5.0	5.0×10^6
	10.0	8.0×10^7
Melon + Sodium Chloride + Sodium Citrate	2.5	3.1×10^5
	5.0	2.5×10^5
	10.0	1.8×10^6

TABLE 3: Morphology & Biochemical Characteristics of the organisms isolated from both the preserved and the control samples of ground melon

S/N	COLONIAL MORPHOLOGY	GRAM STAIN	BIOCHEMICAL REACTIONS							SUGAR FERMENTATION					ISOLATED ORGANISMS
			MOT	CAT	INO	CIT	URE	MET	GLU	SUC	LAC	MAN	MAL		
1	Yellow, Flat, smooth and entire colonies	Gram positive Cocci in clusters	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	A	-	A	A/G	A	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
2	Large convex Shape, mucoid Pinkish colonies	Gram negative coccobacilli	-	+	-	+	+	+	A/G	A	A	A	A	<i>Klebsiella Pneumoniae</i>	
3	Whitish Mold Which later turned black, text is powdered with septate hyphae	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	

KEY

NT = Not Tested

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

It was observed during the period of preservation of the ground melon that the microbial quality of the melon samples treated with salts at various concentrations were fairly constant. This could be due to the action of the preservatives on the microorganisms and the microorganisms needed a longer time to enable them breakdown the bond into smaller pieces that will enhance the gradual changes in the microbial qualities or the stabilities of the melon (Oyolu, 1977; Small *et al*, 1994).

The preservatives used were able to increase the shelf life of the melon because they suppressed the microbial activities and maintained its stability; hence the viable counts of treated samples were lower than the control sample. Amongst the salts used, sodium chloride at a concentration of 10.0% had the highest inhibitory effect on the microorganisms with the least mean plate count of 4.5×10^3 cfu/g (Table 2), while sodium citrate at a concentration of 10.0% had the least inhibitory effect with the mean plate count of 8.0×10^7 cfu/g (Table 2). Moreover, high concentration of sodium chloride coupled with low moisture content of the melon seems to be more effective in maintaining the microbial stability and increasing the shelf life of melon.

The colour of the control sample changed from milk to brown colour with offensive odour after 31days of preservation (Table 1). This could be attributed to the absence of the preservatives which would have reduced the microbial activities and growth since melon act as a good medium for microbial growth due to its high fats and protein content (Abaelu, 1977, Akobundu, 1982 and Orji *et al*, 2006).The colour change noticed in all the

samples treated with various concentrations of the additives after 31 days could be due to the chemical reaction between the additives and the chemical components of the melon. Surprisingly, the sample treated with 10.0% combined sodium chloride and sodium citrate had offensive odour in addition to the colour change (Table 1). This could be due to the fact that higher concentration of sodium citrate enhances microbial growth. This is equally substantiated by the high viable count of 8×10^7 cfu/g recorded at 10.0% concentration of sodium citrate (Table 2).

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